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Ahr controls IDO1 to enforce local tolerance.

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Deletion of AHR in human cells resulted in near complete loss of IDO1. The data support the existence of a mechanism by which local toleragenic force is generated involving IDO1-related metabolite(s), regulated through AHR control of IDO1.